

Type 2 Diabetes Can Be Reversed and Even Cured

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Abstract

Type 2 diabetes (T2D) is a global health burden traditionally regarded as a metabolic disorder driven by insulin resistance, genetics, and lifestyle factors. Although scientific research has made considerable progress in identifying molecular mechanisms and therapeutic strategies, the disease is still widely considered irreversible. These approaches, however, overlook the deeper karmic origins of illness, which explain why patients are unable to restore normal pancreatic function or escape lifelong medical dependence. In essence, most scientific advancements address symptoms rather than uncovering the fundamental cause. Drawing on the teachings of Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu and documented recovery cases, this study provides evidence that T2D is a karmic illness that can be reversed or even cured through the Five Golden Buddhist Practices of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. By consistently eliminating karmic debts and helping spirits ascend, patients can restore cellular function and recover health, offering a transformative path beyond the limits of conventional medicine.

Keywords: Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door; Golden Buddhist Practices; Karma; Spirits; Type 2 Diabetes; Recovery

Introduction

Type 2 diabetes (T2D), also known as non-insulin-dependent diabetes, is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by insulin resistance and relative insulin deficiency, resulting in elevated blood glucose levels [1]. It accounts for more than 90% of all diabetes cases worldwide [2]. This condition results from a combination of genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors that impair the body's ability to regulate blood glucose levels effectively [3].

In T2D, peripheral tissues, particularly muscle and adipose tissue, become resistant to insulin, a hormone produced by pancreatic beta cells that facilitates glucose uptake. Over time, beta cell dysfunction may lead to reduced insulin secretion, exacerbating hyperglycemia [4].

The pathophysiology involves complex interactions, including increased hepatic glucose production, impaired insulin signaling, and chronic inflammation, often linked to obesity [5]. Risk factors include genetic predisposition, sedentary lifestyle, high-calorie diets, and visceral fat accumulation. Symptoms may include polyuria, polydipsia, fatigue, and blurred vision, though many cases remain asymptomatic initially, leading to delayed diagnosis [6]. Complications of uncontrolled T2D are severe, encompassing cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, retinopathy, nephropathy, and increased infection susceptibility [7].

Management typically involves lifestyle modifications, such as weight loss, dietary changes, and physical activity [8], alongside pharmacological interventions like metformin, sulfonylureas [9], or insulin therapy in advanced cases [10]. Early detection and intervention are critical to prevent long-term complications. Ongoing research continues to explore novel therapeutic targets, including incretin-based therapies and gut microbiome modulation, to improve outcomes for individuals with T2D.

In summary, according to current scientific knowledge, T2D is considered non-reversible and incurable. Yet, the guiding principle in medicine is to either cure a disease or reverse its progression.

We previously reported a case in which a patient with a 15-year history of T2D experienced a reduction in fasting blood glucose from 22.0 to 7.1 mmol/L after practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, as taught by Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu [11]. This encouraging outcome motivated the present study, which aims to examine whether this practice can be applied more broadly in T2D management, what therapeutic effects may be achieved, and what mechanisms may underlie them. To address these questions, we present eight of Master Lu's enlightenments together with

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eight clinical cases, offering practical guidance for patients to manage their illness at home in parallel with conventional medical treatment, thereby supporting recovery.

Key Dharma Concepts

For readers unfamiliar with Buddhist terminology, certain concepts may require clarification, for example, Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, life composition, karma, soul, spirit, ghost, Little House, underworld, heaven, human realm, underworld festivals, relationship between sentient beings, sources of karma or karmic obstacle, impact of spirits and Bodhisattva on health, the predestined 369 calamity, life liberation, merits and virtues, and cycle of rebirth. Detailed explanations can be found in our previous publications [11, 12]. For an illustration of the Little House, see [13].

On Master Jun Hong Lu's blog, numerous healing experiences are documented. For the Chinese website, please refer to (<http://www.lujunhong2or.com>). For the English website, please refer to (<https://guanyincitta.com>). Without exception, these cases bear witness to the truth of the Dharma.

Pathogenetic Mechanisms & Solutions

Scientifically, T2D is a chronic, non-communicable metabolic disorder in which genetic, behavioral, and environmental factors interact to drive disease development [14]. The primary mechanism involves functional impairment of pancreatic beta cells and inadequate insulin secretion [15]. However, the root causes of beta cell dysfunction remain unclear [16]. Although diabetes has traditionally been considered manageable but not curable [17], some researchers argue that a cure may be theoretically possible [18]. In summary, science views T2D as a disease with multifactorial etiology and no definitive cure at present.

However, from a Dharma perspective, and based on our previous reports [11], we regard T2D as a karmic disease with manifestations of spirit (a respectful name of ghost). Effective treatment, therefore, requires the removal of both karma and spirit attachments. Once purified of these burdens, health can be naturally restored. Although the Dharma concept is not as widely recognized as modern science, its efficacy in addressing intractable diseases is often superior to conventional medicine [11]. To introduce this perspective, we begin with its fundamental principles. The following section presents eight Q&As in which Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu explains the causes of T2D and outlines the path to recovery.

Q&A 1. How to Resolve Diabetes from the Perspective of Buddhism and the Law of Cause and Effect (Excerpt) [19]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Nov. 27, 2016)

Caller: Master, from the perspective of Buddhism and the law of cause and effect, how can diabetes be resolved?

Master: In fact, there are two types of diabetes. One is hereditary, and the other is acquired. If the parents have diabetes, there are two possibilities. One is karmic debt, and the other is simply that the parents' bodies are weak. If the parents are physically unwell and the diabetes is inherited, you cannot say that the children automatically bear karmic guilt. This is because the human body has two aspects: one is physical illness, and the other is spiritual illness. If a physical illness is passed on to the child, that is a form of heredity, and you cannot say the child is bad because of it.

But if the parents carry spirits or have committed killing karma—say the father or mother once ran a butcher shop, sold pork, or owned a restaurant—then if they had diabetes and their children also develop diabetes, that is definitely related to shared karmic debt. On the other hand, if the parents were honest and upright all their lives but simply did not control their sugar intake, then their diabetes arises from that habit. As one doctor explained, if you binge on sugar and chocolate at a young age, you may develop diabetes. This is because of excessive sugar consumption, and it usually manifests in the 30s. Such cases are not congenital. Congenital cases are hereditary, but if you know your parents have diabetes and you strictly control your sugar intake, you might avoid diabetes for your entire life. That is what doctors say.

Caller: I understand. Then, if diabetes is karmic, is it the result of killing karma committed in this life?

Master: Diabetes is not strongly related to killing karma. It is essentially due to excessive consumption of sugar and sweet foods, leading to insufficient insulin secretion. Although diabetes is a “killer,” the karmic weight behind it is not very heavy. If you look at diseases like liver cancer, when the liver is damaged, that is definitely tied to killing karma. But the stomach and spleen are not heavily related; they may not involve killing karma. The liver and kidneys, however, are extremely important, as are the heart and brain. With the heart, there are also congenital and acquired cases. Some children are born with serious heart defects and must undergo surgery, but they live only a short life. That is because they came to repay karmic debts, and once their debts are repaid, they pass away.

Q&A 2. Diabetes is a karmic illness, requiring diligent recitation to eliminate karma [20]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on July 5, 2014)

Caller: Master, could you please check a man born in 1982, the Year of the Dog? Does he have a spirit attached?

Master: Yes, there is a spirit. He has problems with hemorrhoids, urination, and the urinary system.

Caller: Ah? He has so many problems... How many Little Houses does he need to recite?

Master: 26 sheets.

Caller: He has diabetes. Does this have anything to do with it?

Master: Yes.

Caller: For diabetes, how many Little Houses should he recite?

Master: Quite a lot. Diabetes is a chronic illness, and generally it is a karmic illness. He must recite diligently to eliminate karma. There is no other way.

Caller: Okay. Should he recite them in batches?

Master: Yes, 21 sheets per batch.

Caller: Alright, I understand. Thank you, Master. Gratitude to Bodhisattva for the blessings!

Master: Alright, goodbye.

Q&A 3. Diabetes requires both recitation of Buddhist scriptures and proper medical control [21]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Feb. 19, 2012)

Caller: My father has diabetes. In this case, how should he recite?

Master: The same way, recite the *Heart Sutra* and the *Great Compassion Mantra*, also recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, and offer Little Houses to his karmic creditors. The principle is the same.

Caller: How many times should he recite daily? He is already over sixty.

Master: As many times as he can. For diabetes, the illness must also be controlled well. For example, 21 times of the *Heart Sutra*, 21 times of the *Great Compassion Mantra*, and 3 times of the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*.

Q&A 4. The basic daily recitation of the Buddhist for diabetic patients (Except) [22]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Oct. 9, 2011)

Caller: My mother feels pain in her body, her eyesight is not good, and she also has diabetes. How should she help herself?

Master: First, she must recite the *Heart Sutra*, the *Great Compassion Mantra*, and the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* well. Recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* 2 times daily. She must start reciting by herself. In addition, Little Houses must be continuously recited and offered to her karmic creditors. Start with a first batch of 27 sheets.

Q&A 5. Diabetes: Recite Little Houses in batches of 49, combined with life liberation [23]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Jan. 6, 2012)

Caller: A woman born in 1969 has diabetes, and it is quite serious now. I advised her to recite in batches of 49 Little Houses and also perform life liberation. She herself has faith, recites the *Great Compassion Mantra* daily, and her mother also helps by reciting Little Houses. Is this okay?

Master: Yes, that is fine.

Caller: So just continue like this?

Master: Yes. If her spiritual strength is insufficient, she must persist.

Caller: Okay, so continue with 49 Little Houses per batch, plus life liberation, right?

Master: Correct!

Q&A 6. Proper diet for diabetes (Excerpt) [24]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on April 6, 2012)

Caller: Master Lu, how do you feel about my energy field?

Master: I feel that you are not awakened at all! Your mind is not clear. You must diligently recite the *Heart Sutra*. You are so young, yet you are already on insulin. Don't you realize how dangerous and serious this is?

Caller: I have already been hospitalized once for a blood clot. At the age of 31, it was because of insulin...

Master: Think about it! And yet you still... Ai, you are really not awakened! You must recite diligently!

Caller: When I vowed to be a vegetarian, my mother said, "See, you can not eat sweet food, you can not eat meat, so you can only eat a little bit of vegetables."

Master: Oh, don't listen to your mother! Eat less! Let me tell you: in the morning and at noon you can eat until full, but in the evening you can only drink a little soup. Even if you are hungry, at night you can continue with lotus root starch. That lotus root starch is excellent. Dissolve it with a bit of sugar substitute, and whenever you feel hungry, eat it until you are full, then go to sleep. Keep this up for a while, and you will gradually no longer need insulin injections...

Caller: Oh! That is wonderful!

Q&A 7. For diabetes, do not eat four hours before sleep; soak feet more often [25]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on July 26, 2013)

Caller: My mother has diabetes...

Master: She must not eat anything four hours before bedtime. Every day she should walk for half an hour. You will see improvement. She also needs to soak her feet. You recite 3 Little Houses for her karmic creditors each week. Also, ask your mother whether she has ever had an abortion. If she lost a child, recite 21 Little Houses for each child. Once that is done, her diabetes will improve significantly. Believe me.

Q&A 8. Diabetes: Vow of a large number of Little Houses, careful diet, and post-meal activity [26]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on July 16, 2017)

Caller: An elderly mother has hereditary diabetes, and her heart is not very good. She wishes to make a vow to recite a large batch of Little Houses, such as 500 or 800 sheets, to eliminate karmic debts. Is that possible?

Master: Yes, it is.

Caller: So she can continue to make such vows and recite continuously, right?

Master: Yes, keep making vows and reciting, continue until she ascends to Heaven.

Caller: What should she pay attention to in her diet? She is a vegetarian. She does not dare to take too much insulin, but now she already needs daily injections.

Master: She should eat small portions but more frequently. For those with insufficient insulin secretion, that is the right way. If she feels hungry, drink some soup, eat some vegetarian dishes, and add a little oil. Whenever hunger strikes, eat that. There is no other way. Also, no food within four hours before bedtime. After each meal, she must walk and cannot sleep. She must force herself to walk.

Caller: Okay.

From a Dharma perspective, T2D is a karmic illness requiring the elimination of both karmic debts and spirit attachments. Master Lu's teachings emphasize the Five Golden Buddhist Practices—making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, performing life liberation, repenting of wrongdoings and refraining from doing them, and studying *Buddhism in Plain Terms*—as the pathway to recovery. When combined with lifestyle adjustments and conventional medical care, these practices enable patients to purify karma, restore cellular function, and achieve significant improvement or even complete reversal of diabetes.

Results

The following are eight case presentations by practitioners of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

Case 1. My husband has completely recovered from his 36-year-long hereditary diabetes after practicing Buddhism for nearly four years

My husband had suffered from hereditary diabetes for 36 years, along with many other health problems such as high blood pressure, acid reflux, high uric acid, and gout. Whenever he experienced acid reflux, he would feel chest pain, and his blood pressure would shoot up to over 180, often requiring emergency visits to the hospital late at night. Because of high uric acid levels, his body could not expel it through urine, which led to gout.

In the early stage, only his right heel was swollen and painful, but it gradually worsened to the point that he twice developed swelling and pain in both elbows so severe that he could not move them, and had to rush to the emergency room at midnight and be hospitalized immediately. This severely affected his daily life and work.

For 36 years, he endured unbearable physical and mental suffering from diabetes and other illnesses, not knowing when he would ever see hope again.

In 2015, my aunt living overseas, called to introduce us to Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. In June of that year, after we attended a Dharma conference in Hong Kong, my husband's persistent foot pain that had lasted for six months completely disappeared. Since then, we have been diligently practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, reciting Buddhist scriptures and reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms* every day, vowing to perform life liberation every month and eat vegetarian meals for ten days each month.

In July 2016 (one year after beginning Buddhist practice), during a follow-up check, his blood sugar level had dramatically dropped from 22 to 5.5 mmol/L. On July 21, the day before Guan Yin Bodhisattva's Enlightenment Day, the doctor told him that starting the next day, he could stop injecting insulin and instead take only one very mild oral diabetes pill a day. We were deeply grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for this precious gift on Her Enlightenment Day.

We are profoundly grateful to Namó the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva for Her compassion, and to our greatly compassionate Master Jun Hong Lu for His blessings.

In February this year, i.e., four years later after practicing Buddhism, during a follow-up visit, the doctor told us that my husband could stop taking the oral diabetes medicine. His 36-year diabetes has been completely cured!

Meanwhile, his high blood pressure, acid reflux, and gout have all returned to normal as well.

It is truly miraculous! For someone who had suffered from chronic illness for so long, this is almost impossible! Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door truly benefits whoever practices it!

We sincerely express our deepest gratitude and respectfully pay homage to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, who hears the cries of the suffering, and to the "Four Golden Buddhist Practices" of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, which are truly efficacious!

Shared by: N159

Case 2. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is incredibly effective — my diabetes and other chronic illnesses gradually healed

Before I started practicing Buddhism, I was plagued by many illnesses: I had suffered from diabetes for nearly 20 years, severe insomnia for more than 10 years, and my heart, liver, and kidneys were in poor condition, which caused swelling in both of my legs. I also had cervical spondylosis, frozen shoulder, and very poor memory. Since the age of 50, I had been constantly tormented by illnesses and unbearable suffering.

I wondered why fate was so unfair to me. While my peers were all healthy, I was suffering from so much pain. I did not understand why. At that time, I knew nothing about the law of cause and effect, not realizing that all the sufferings I endured in this life were the results of karmic seeds I had planted in past lives. As the saying goes, "To know the causes of the past, look at what you are experiencing in this life."

At the time when I was in the deepest pain and despair, the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva mercifully allowed me to encounter Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. In October 2017, a fellow Buddhist practitioner, L, introduced it to me online. After hearing so many real-life testimonials, I was shocked! Could such a wonderful thing truly exist in the world? Could one change one's destiny simply by making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation? I decided to give it a try. Under practitioner L's guidance, I began to sincerely recite Buddhist scriptures. It turned out to be incredibly effective. The Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva brought hope into my painful life and let me see the light!

On December 9, 2017, just before dawn, I was in a half-asleep state when I vaguely saw the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva! I knew that this was Her compassionate blessing upon me. Miraculously, from that day on, my insomnia gradually improved!

Since practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, my diabetes has basically been cured, with my blood sugar now stably within the normal range of 5–6. My insomnia has completely disappeared. I often sleep soundly through the night. My heart palpitations have been effectively controlled, my back pain has greatly improved, and my cervical spondylosis and frozen shoulder have healed on their own! Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is truly miraculous!

On December 10, 2017, with the support of fellow practitioners, I set up a Buddhist altar at home and invited the Bodhisattva into my house. Since then, I have offered incense every day. My home is filled with the Buddha's light, and my days are filled with Dharma joy! I became even more diligent in cultivating my mind and practicing Buddhism. Every day, I listen to Master Lu's recordings, complete my daily recitations, recite Little Houses, and read *Buddhism in Plain Terms*.

At that time, my left leg was in severe pain and very swollen. I am deeply grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva and to Master Lu for their compassion. In a dream, they came to heal me! Although I could not clearly see who the two holy figures were, my mind told me that they were the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu. Master Lu once enlightened us: "When you are suffering the most, I will reach out my hand to pull you up!"

He truly did. It was like giving me charcoal in the snow!

After learning Buddhism, I often reflected on my past and realized that I had done many wrong things. I used to have a terrible temper, often losing my patience and yelling at my husband. He is an honest and introverted man who rarely speaks, sometimes not saying a word for several days. This made me even angrier, and I would sometimes scold him and complain about him to others.

After listening to Master Lu's many teachings, I understood that the conflicts between my husband and me were caused by karmic grievances accumulated over many lifetimes. Once I understood this, I started reciting the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* to dissolve our karmic conflicts, and I also recited the *Heart Sutra* for him, praying to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to bless him with wisdom. At the same time, I offered Little Houses to the spirits attached to him. Gradually, both of our personalities began to change. We started to communicate more and talk peacefully with each other. This was the amazing power of the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* and the Little Houses!

In this human world, we often encounter worries and suffering. We cannot change others; we can only change ourselves. Master Lu teaches us how to adjust our mindset, reminding us that nothing is truly difficult if we are sincere. When the mind is correct, the path will be smooth. A correct mindset can make life peaceful and smooth. I am deeply grateful to Namó the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, who saves the suffering, and to our Master!

I made a few great vows. In this life, I will

- (1). Follow Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu to cultivate my mind and practice Buddhism, never quitting;
- (2). Be a lifelong vegetarian, refrain from killing;
- (3). Live an ascetic life;
- (4). Diligently help sentient beings, and create merits and virtues!

I am grateful to our great Master for bringing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door to the human world, bringing the Dharma and blessings to all sentient beings! Thank you, Master, for sacrificing yourself to spread the Dharma, allowing us to have good health, happy families, a prosperous country, and a peaceful society!

Shared by: M160

Case 3. After 15 years of trying every possible method without success, my diabetes finally returned to normal through the miraculous Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door

I was diagnosed with diabetes after a health check-up in 2006. The hospital called me, saying my fasting blood glucose was 15.8 mmol/L and urged me to undergo further tests. Stubbornly, I believed that high blood sugar did not necessarily mean diabetes, so I paid little attention to it. Even in 2010, when my fasting glucose rose to 21.6 mmol/L, I still dismissed it. It wasn't until three unusual episodes in the second half of 2012 that I finally realized something was seriously wrong.

One afternoon, I noticed persistent dampness and intense itching in my private area for several days. Scratching made it worse, and even hot water did not relieve it. Oddly, after a week or two, the itching stopped on its own. Not long after, while rinsing my feet with tap water before bathing one night, a sudden chill ran up from my feet to my whole body, leaving me shivering. Soon afterward, my weight

plummeted from over 80 kg to around 65 kg in less than a month. That is when the thought of diabetic complications first crossed my mind, and I began to panic. From then on, my once warm hands and feet were icy cold for over ten years.

I started a long and exhausting search for a cure, trying every treatment I could find, but none worked. What worked for others had no effect on me. For example:

I visited a specialist and took Chinese herbal medicine for almost a year, spending over 100 CNY daily. My glucose once dropped to around 7 mmol/L, but quickly rose again after stopping the herbs.

I tried drinking a herbal infusion said to lower blood sugar. I consumed over a dozen of kilograms of it while continuing Western medication, but my glucose did not drop. Instead, it continued rising.

A classmate gave me a "secret prescription" from a medical professor. My classmate had recovered after 78 doses, but even after I took 280 doses, my glucose stayed over 10 mmol/L. I then tried another formula for thin-type diabetes, taking over 100 more doses, yet my glucose remained high and kept rising.

Later, I heard that drinking water infused with certain tree leaves could treat diabetes. In my confusion, I found new hope. So, I returned to my hometown, climbed a 50-year-old tree, and chopped down over 150 kilograms of leaves, happily bringing them back to the city. I brewed the leaves into tea, but it was awful—bitter, astringent, with a strange taste that was hard to endure. Still, for the sake of curing my diabetes, I forced myself to drink it, continuing for nearly a year until all 150 kg of leaves were used up, but the results were deeply disappointing.

Everything in this world is karmically arranged. Just when I was at my lowest, a miracle happened. I encountered the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. I came to understand the law of cause and effect: all the misfortunes of this life stem from karmic debts of past lives. Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door felt like rain after a long drought, and the compassionate Master Lu is truly a living Bodhisattva who soothes our suffering hearts. Through making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, releasing captive lives, and studying *Buddhism in Plain Terms*—the Four Golden Buddhist Practices—I began to eliminate my karmic debts and dissolve karmic obstacles.

Before my home Buddhist altar, I made solemn vows:

- (1). Respect my Master and the Dharma;
- (2). Follow the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Jun Hong Lu for life;
- (3). Stay dedicated to one Dharma Door and never regress;
- (4). Be a vegetarian for life and never kill;
- (5). Devote my life to spreading Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door to save sentient beings and protect its Dharma centers;
- (6). Release 100,000 fish.

I began practicing diligently every day. After offering my first batch of 108 Little Houses to my karmic creditors, my body felt incredibly light, and my blood glucose immediately dropped to 5.4 mmol/L. It was miraculous! Then I continued offering Little Houses in batches of 21. One morning at around 4 a.m., an inner message told me to recite 464 Little Houses. I knew it was guidance from the Bodhisattva. I vowed to complete 470 Little Houses for my karmic

creditors.

Gratitude to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, and to our selfless Master Jun Hong Lu, I have found unprecedented peace and serenity. Now my blood glucose has remained steady at around 6.5 mmol/L, something I never dreamed possible before.

Currently, I join fellow practitioners twice a week in an online group study of *Buddhism in Plain Terms*. It helps me stay diligent, strengthens my faith, and keeps my practice on the right path. Studying together allows us to encourage each other and make solid progress.

I hope that all predestined sentient beings, especially those suffering from diabetes like I once did, can believe in the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. It is absolutely real. As long as you have faith and practice the Four Golden Buddhist Practices, miracles will happen. May all sentient beings board the Bodhi Dharma ship of Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Jun Hong Lu, attain enlightenment, transcend the Six Realms, ascend to the Four Sagely Realms, and reach the Guan Yin Citta Pure Land of supreme perfect enlightenment.

Shared by: X161

Case 4. Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is true and effective — reversing diabetes with the Five Golden Buddhist Practices

Today, with immense gratitude, I would like to share how I brought my diabetes under good control within three years by practicing the Five Golden Buddhist Practices.

In 2021, I was 53 years old, which was also a predestined “369 calamity” year for me. In March that year, I was diagnosed with a fasting blood glucose of 15 mmol/L and a post-meal blood glucose of 25 mmol/L. After 10 days of insulin treatment in the hospital, my blood sugar was brought under temporary control. I switched from insulin injections to taking one diabetes pill per day, but I could only eat 75 grams of rice per meal and had to exercise two hours after each meal. After several months, my weight dropped from 52.5 kg to 46 kg.

Seeing me pale, thin, and malnourished, my colleagues and family members all asked what was wrong with me. At that time, I was on the verge of a mental breakdown. I wondered why, despite reciting Buddhist scriptures and releasing captive animals every day, Guan Yin Bodhisattva did not bless me. I even began to doubt the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and had thoughts of giving up. Looking back, I was very ignorant. I did not realize that karmic obstacles had ripened in my “369 calamity” year, and because I lacked enough merits and virtues as well as Little Houses to counteract them, my body had to endure the karmic retribution. Every day, I knelt in front of the Buddhist altar in tears, praying for Guan Yin Bodhisattva to save me. But Bodhisattvas do not interfere with the cause and effect.

Although I had few merits and virtues, I had sincere faith. The Buddhas respond to sincerity. Under the compassionate guidance of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, I desperately searched Master Lu’s blog for cases about diabetes. I saw that fellow practitioners not only made vows, recited scriptures, released captive lives, and performed good deeds, but also diligently studied *Buddhism in Plain Terms*. Reflecting on myself, although I had practiced Buddhism from 2016 to 2021 (five years), I had never seriously studied *Buddhism in Plain Terms*. I did not observe precepts, and my body, speech, and mind kept creating negative karma.

I was deeply touched by the great vows shared by other practitioners on the blog. Master said that when your vow power surpasses your karmic obstacles, you will definitely receive blessings from Guan Yin Bodhisattva, Master, and all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas. So I made a firm resolution and knelt before my Buddhist altar to make these great vows:

- (1). Recite 1,000 Little Houses for my karmic creditors within one year;
- (2). Release 100,000 fish within ten years;
- (3). Study *Buddhism in Plain Terms*;
- (4). Perform Dharma propagation.

After making these vows, I practiced diligently every day, and a miracle finally happened to me. My fasting blood sugar gradually dropped from 15 mmol/L to 6.5 mmol/L. My face became rosy again, and my weight increased from 46 kg to 56 kg. Previously, I could only eat miscellaneous grains, but now I can eat white rice, porridge, and white bread. A friend who was diagnosed with diabetes at the same time is still eating miscellaneous grains but still struggles to control her blood sugar. I deeply realized that Buddhists are blessed by Bodhisattvas, while non-Buddhists can only follow their predetermined fate. Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is truly miraculous and efficacious!

I am grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva for blessing me, and grateful to my benevolent Master for imparting the Five Golden Buddhist Practices to us, which allowed me to personally experience the incredible power of this Dharma Door. Just as Master often enlightened us, vow power is very important. No matter how big or small your vows are, once you make them, Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, and our benevolent Master will bless us to overcome hardships. When I knelt at my altar and uttered, “I am grateful to Namó the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva who hears the cries of the world,” I was already sobbing uncontrollably: “I will definitely cultivate diligently, follow Master’s teachings, respect my Master, repay my karmic debts, eliminate karma, and persist in propagating the Dharma to save others, so that one day I can be free from all debts and return the heaven home with my Master!”

After going through the karmic obstacle of my “369 calamity,” I truly realized that impermanence is right beside us. Karma is like a shark that stares at me relentlessly. If I am careless, it will bite and drag me down. I feel extremely fortunate to have encountered the Dharma in this lifetime. When facing calamities, I can use the Five Golden Buddhist Practices taught by the Master to save myself, with the most compassionate Bodhisattva protecting me. Practicing Buddhism is the wisest decision I have ever made in this life. Being able to practice the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and to encounter the Master who loves us most is the greatest blessing of my life.

Shared by: L162

Case 5. Miraculously returning my high blood sugar to normal through the Three Golden Buddhist Practices

In 2015, I was troubled by diabetes. My post-meal blood glucose reached over 18 mmol/L. I had to take medicine every day and receive intravenous drips for ten days every month just to keep it under control. I even developed complications. My vision dropped to 0.3, and I was considering undergoing surgery.

One day in May 2015, after I took my granddaughter to kindergarten and came back, I saw some people talking on the roadside, so I went up and asked if they were Buddhist practitioners. After they replied, I said that my grandmas and great-grandma had all believed in Buddhism. Having just moved here from my hometown with no one to rely on, I wanted to find a temple to offer incense and bow. That fellow practitioner then invited me to her home, where she gave me books, CDs, and a player, and patiently shared joyful stories of Dharma practice. She also taught me how to make prayers while reciting. I am still deeply grateful to her to this day. That was how I first formed a connection with Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

I had never been to school and was illiterate, so I followed the player and recited word by word carefully every day. After doing this for several days, one day during a nap, I dreamed that Master Lu came to my home. The feeling was wonderful.

On October 1, the practitioner who introduced me to the Dharma Door gifted me Buddhist altar supplies and a Bodhisattva statue. I began offering incense daily and prayed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to grant me wisdom. I slowly followed the player and could recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* two or three times a day. I also often went to release captive lives with other practitioners. I could basically finish my daily recitations.

Later, that practitioner also gave me blank Little House papers, red cloth, and a red pen, and taught me how to make red dots on them. At that time, my eyes were so blurry that I could not even place the dots on the Little Houses.

After about a year of practice, I slowly began to be able to place the dots. Once, I dreamed that Master Lu had opened a large hospital where many people were eating together. Master said to me, "Why don't you go get a bowl? There is a big pot of noodles. Go and get some quickly." I took a bowl and filled it with a large serving of noodles. When I woke up, I was deeply moved and very grateful. Master has been blessing me all along, helping me eliminate karmic obstacles and extend my lifespan.

Practicing Buddhism is truly wonderful. I am so grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva, to Master, and to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door!

I decided to apply the Three Golden Buddhist Practices to lower my blood sugar. I vowed to recite and offer 1,800 Little Houses to my karmic creditors, and I continued releasing captive lives as conditions allowed (I have been doing so since I started practicing, though I no longer remember the exact number).

By the time I had recited about 800 Little Houses, our workplace arranged a health checkup. Because I had diabetes, I specifically asked the endocrinology doctor to check my blood sugar. The doctor said, "You do not have diabetes. Everything is normal, nothing is wrong." Skeptical, I said, "Really? I had diabetes, and my blood sugar used to be very high—over 18 mmol/L after meals and more than 10 mmol/L before meals." The doctor replied, "Here are your test results. Your blood sugar is 4.7 mmol/L. Everything is normal. Do you have any discomfort now?" I said, "No, nothing." The next day, I went to a private hospital in my hometown for another test, and the result still showed 4.7 mmol/L before meals.

The Three Golden Buddhist Practices are truly miraculous, and the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is real and effective. I did not expect that before I even finished fulfilling my vows, my blood sugar would return to normal. My eyes are no longer as blurry as before, and I can

see clearly again. I am deeply grateful to Bodhisattva and to Master.

Without Buddhism, I would have been tortured by all kinds of diabetic complications. I might not even still be alive. It was Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master who gave me a second life. In this lifetime, I must cultivate my mind and practice diligently, never quit, and become one of the hands and eyes of Guan Yin Bodhisattva to save more sentient beings who have affinities with Buddha.

Practicing Buddhism can truly change destiny, and it costs nothing. I sincerely hope that my sharing can encourage more sentient beings with affinities to Buddha to pick up the scriptures, learn Buddhism, recite mantras and sutras, and be free from suffering and attain happiness.

I will bear my own karmic obstacles, and will not let others bear them for me.

Shared by: Z163

Case 6. My Husband's Blood Sugar Normalized *via* Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door

I previously reported my healing experience with limb myasthenia gravis after practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door [27]. Here, I will share how I helped my husband recover from his T2D.

In 2016, my husband turned 63, entering his "369 predestined calamity" age.

He normally does not eat snacks, but suddenly had a craving for them, eating from morning to night, and eating snacks before he went to sleep. The more he ate, the thinner he became. I felt something was wrong and took him to the hospital for a checkup. His diagnosis shocked me. His pre-meal blood sugar was 18.2, post-meal blood sugar was 28.2 mmol/L, and a variety of other indexes were bad. He was prescribed many medicines. One of the medicines, metformin tablets, has significant side effects and directly affects liver and kidney health.

There is a saying that "a long illness makes you a good doctor". In my case, I have been ill for a long time, so I have taken many medicines to treat lupus erythematosus. My lupus erythematosus was not cured, but the side effects of the medicines caused myasthenia gravis. Hence, I opposed my husband taking too many medicines.

As a result of studying Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, I learned that there are two types of illnesses: physical and karmic (spiritual) illnesses. Physical illnesses can be treated by doctors, but karmic illnesses are very difficult to treat with medicine alone. In order to cure karmic illnesses, one must implement the Five Golden Buddhist Practices: making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, performing life liberation, reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, and repenting of wrongdoings and refraining from doing them. Only by removing karma can karmic (spiritual) illness be cured. As diabetes is also a karmic disease, I convinced my husband to recite Buddhist scriptures for healing.

In the years he has served me, he has witnessed how I have evolved from being a bedridden patient with no strength, needing assistance, to a healthy person who is now frisky and ready to propagate the Dharma. He also felt that our Dharma Door was incredibly efficacious and decided to join me in practicing Buddhism. I can not tell you how happy I was to see that he was determined to become a vegetarian and recite the Buddhist scriptures. In order to encourage him and let him witness Buddhism's magic, I also quietly helped him recite Little

Houses.

In less than 3 months, without taking a single pill, his blood sugar dropped from 18.2 to 5.3 mmol/L, completely normal! He witnessed the miracle himself and became more confident in Buddhism. During the past 7 years, he kept reciting the Buddhist scriptures, eating vegetarian food, and releasing lives. Despite never deliberately avoiding sugar, his blood sugar remains at about 5.3 mmol/L.

What is more surprising is that his gout, which had bothered him for more than 10 years, has been cured.

Shared by: Z46

Case 7. Unexpected recovery from diabetes in my late sixties with nasopharyngeal carcinoma after practicing Buddhism

Although I had been offering incense to the Buddhas and had taken refuge in the Three Jewels many years ago, I did not know how to recite Buddhist scriptures and understand the teachings of Buddhism. So when karmic obstacles erupted, I still could not overcome them.

In May 2014, I was diagnosed with nasopharyngeal carcinoma and required 30 sessions of radiotherapy. Looking back now, the pain from radiotherapy was truly unbearable. That bone-deep agony made me lose all hope in life and all confidence in the future. Just when I was in utter despair, I was aimlessly browsing the internet and happened to meet the fellow Buddhist practitioner who later guided me. Her warmth and care at that time were so touching and heartwarming. That was how I joined Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

Since then, I have felt bathed in the Buddha's light, as though I had stepped out of darkness into the bright sunshine. Because of my illness, I could hardly sit up and could only lie down or lean forward while listening to Master Lu's recorded Dharma talks. At first, I could not recite mantras and sutras and found it very uncomfortable to move my mouth, so I just lay there and listened, reciting a little bit at a time. Gradually, I was able to sit up.

Back then, my physical condition was extremely poor. It took me half an hour just to go to the bathroom, and my legs would go numb afterward. My throat hurt like swallowing razor blades every day. Later, I learned how to recite Buddhist scriptures. I also received a small Buddhist altar from a fellow practitioner. When I recited in front of it, I felt even more blessed by the Bodhisattva. I then learned how to recite and offer Little Houses. Before the Lunar New Year, I went to the hospital for a follow-up checkup, and all my indicators were good. This made me stronger and gave me greater faith in practicing Buddhism.

I consulted fellow practitioners and learned that miscarried children needed to be liberated, so I recited 44 Little Houses for them. After that, I no longer dreamed of the child, and my back pain disappeared. My health recovered very quickly, and I felt lighter and more energetic every day.

It was the Bodhisattva who saved me from the abyss of suffering. I am truly grateful to the Bodhisattva, to Master Lu for bringing such a wonderful Dharma Door to the world, and to the fellow practitioner who guided me to Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

On March 30, 2025, I had a comprehensive check-up again. The doctor was surprised by the results. Even young people rarely recover so well and so fast, yet I am 67 years old.

I had diabetes for nine years, but this time the check-up showed that my pancreas was normal, and I no longer needed any diabetes medication.

My liver, gallbladder, pancreas, spleen, and kidneys were all normal. I used to have severe fatty liver, and there were ridges on my fingernails, but they have greatly reduced now. I feel wonderful. I no longer feel heavy in my legs when walking, and I walk lightly and easily. I also had chronic stomach problems; my stomach often hurt, but now it no longer does. I also had heart disease and high blood pressure. Before reciting mantras and sutras, I had to rely on medication to lower my blood pressure, but now I do not need it anymore.

Before practicing Buddhism, my family was disharmonious. I once suffered from depression and even had repeated suicidal thoughts. Now my family is harmonious, my depression has disappeared, and I am filled with Dharma joy every day as I study and recite Buddhist scriptures. The Buddha and Bodhisattvas are truly Great Healers.

I am an elderly woman over sixty with cancer and many illnesses, yet I have recovered so well. The Bodhisattva is so compassionate, and the Master is so compassionate. If I do not diligently practice Buddhism from now on, I would be unworthy of the Bodhisattva, unworthy of the Master, and even more unworthy of the fellow practitioner who patiently, tirelessly, and lovingly guided me step by step into Buddhism.

Shared by: L165

Case 8. The Five Golden Buddhist Practices greatly improved my diabetes and its complications

In the summer of 2020, I had a blood sugar test, and the result was high—around 17.9 mmol/L. I did not take it seriously, just took some medication, and did not pursue treatment or watch my diet.

In 2021, at the age of 48, it was my zodiac year, and I was also clashing with Tai Sui Bodhisattva. One day, my blood sugar suddenly spiked to 28 mmol/L, and even insulin injections could not bring it down. I was urgently admitted to the hospital for IV treatment.

On the first day, my blood sugar was tested every hour, and if it did not drop, they added a dose of medication to the IV. After 24 tests in 24 hours, my blood sugar still had not decreased, so they kept adding more medication. Eventually, the doctors had no choice but to add hypoglycemic drugs to the IV and attach an insulin pump to my abdomen. During meals, they would adjust the pump to deliver insulin faster, then slow it down afterward. The doctors said my condition had likely been developing for over a decade, but I had not paid attention to it, which led to this severity. The treatment process was excruciatingly painful.

The high blood sugar triggered complications, including retinal hemorrhages and severe numbness in my limbs. I could not stamp my feet or clap my hands because doing so caused intense pain and numbness. I felt depressed and hopeless, as if a heavy stone was pressing on my chest, making it hard to breathe. At night, I had to sit up to catch my breath, feeling suffocated. During that time, I was so fragile that I even thought about giving up on life.

Due to the severity of my diabetes, I lost over 10 kilograms in weight. Looking back, I was like a terminally ill elderly person. Diabetes made my body feel cold. I could not use a fan or open a window. Once, while chatting with a neighbor at my doorstep, I

accidentally brushed against her hand. She screamed in shock, saying my body felt as cold as a snake.

The retinal hemorrhages caused by high blood sugar required treatment. I underwent four laser treatments at a provincial hospital, which caused swelling in my eyes. Each laser session damaged my vision further, leaving me with a visual acuity of only 0.08. With such poor eyesight, I could not see light-colored objects, only darker ones. I recall mistaking a neighbor in a white shirt for a dog approaching me until I got closer.

After the laser treatments, I went to the hospital for injections to restore my vision and reduce swelling. Each injection, administered near my eye, cost 4,000 CNY and only worked for a month. My vision improved slightly. My left eye reached 0.5, and my right eye 0.3. However, after a month, it would revert to its original state. The injections could not truly heal my eyes.

Later, I had the good fortune to meet Buddhist practitioner S, a fellow villager who introduced me to Buddhism. I told her I had taken refuge and was chanting “Amitufo (Amitabha Buddha’s name)”. She shared that she also recited Buddhist scriptures and introduced me to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, gifting me some Buddhist texts. Although my vision was poor, I was eager to recite the scriptures, feeling like I had found a lifeline I had to hold onto tightly.

I prayed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to help me see the scriptures clearly. I started learning to recite in late June and began chanting the Little House on July 14. As a diabetic, I had to exercise for an hour half an hour after meals, totaling 4-5 hours of exercise daily, which made it hard to focus on chanting. After two months, I memorized the scriptures and could recite them while exercising. From the moment I woke up, I chanted until late at night, often until 10:30 p.m., for over ten hours a day.

Initially, I could only recite a few Little Houses per day due to my unfamiliarity with the scriptures, but I never stopped, as this was my last hope. I vowed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to release 1,200 fish and 49 turtles within a year and to help print Buddhist books.

I desperately wanted to read *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, but my vision was hampered by retinal hemorrhages, cataracts, and presbyopia. These made it nearly impossible to see the small text. I earnestly prayed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to let me read the text clearly. Miraculously, as I kept praying, I could gradually make out the words. I recited three chapters daily, though it took a long time and was straining, but at least I could see the text. I felt that the Bodhisattva had heard my vows and granted me this opportunity. Everything I wished for and prayed for, Guan Yin Bodhisattva saw and heard.

After starting to chant, I became so focused that I did not want to waste time talking. When my family spoke to me, I would just nod or shake my head. They grew frustrated, feeling I was too absorbed in chanting, but I was determined to eliminate my karmic obstacles. I realize now that I was overly attached at the time. As a new practitioner, I lacked wisdom and balance in my approach. I have since adjusted, making time to communicate with my family.

With gratitude for my family’s support and the blessings of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, I set up a Buddhist altar at home on October 22. I made vows

- (1). Be a vegetarian for life, never kill;
- (2). Release animals as opportunities arise;

- (3). Practice Buddhism diligently, never waver;
- (4). Aim to attain enlightenment in this lifetime;
- (5). Recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* five times daily to repent my karmic obstacles (now increased to seven times).

I began reciting Little Houses for my karmic creditors, starting with batches of 21, and after completing 10 batches, I vowed to chant 800 sheets. After finishing those, I vowed another 800 sheets, determined to keep going.

Initially, I could recite 1-2 Little Houses daily, then 4-5, and now 8-9 sheets. Since I do not work, I dedicate myself fully to chanting, not only for myself but also for my child and husband. After about a year of chanting, my energy returned.

Diabetes had left me weak, with numb limbs and blurry vision. Previously, I needed 4-5 hours of exercise after meals; now, 2-3 hours suffice. My vision stabilized, no longer foggy, though diet still affects it slightly. I feel much better overall. I had lost over 10 kg due to high blood sugar, but after a year, I regained 2-2.5 kg. After two years, I fully regained the lost 10 kg. I was filled with Dharma joy!

In 2023, I vowed to release 3,600 fish and 108 turtles. Through Master’s teachings, I recalled that my grandfather had created killing karma. Before studying Buddhism, I was ignorant, but now, with the Dharma and Master’s guidance, I practice, repent, chant, and release animals.

Now, I feel completely different—energetic, with no numbness in my limbs and slightly improved vision. I no longer need insulin injections. I watch my diet a bit, and have a good appetite. I used to have nightmares about deceased villagers following me, but after years of chanting, those stopped.

Recently, a fellow practitioner shared Master’s teaching: “Not having an abortion does not mean you and your husband have not lost a child. Sometimes, when an embryo forms, a spirit enters. Many people use methods, like medication, that can terminate a pregnancy, and those are considered lost children (Wenda20130517 42:01).” Upon hearing this, I immediately recited and offered 21 Little Houses for the spirit of an aborted child. After offering them, my eyes felt remarkably comfortable—an immediate effect! It was truly different!

We must follow Master’s teachings to reduce our karmic debts. As obstacles clear, sharing the Dharma becomes smoother. For the rest of my life, I will follow the Master’s guidance, eliminate my karma, and share this wonderful, cost-free Dharma with more people to benefit them.

Shared by: Y166

These 8 real-life cases of individuals with diabetes who experienced dramatic health improvements or complete recovery after practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. These cases describe long histories of poorly controlled or severe diabetes, often with complications such as high blood pressure, kidney disease, gout, retinopathy, neuropathy, and even cancer, that persisted despite extensive medical treatment. After adopting the “Five Golden Buddhist Practices” (making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, performing life liberation, repenting of wrongdoings and refraining from doing them, and studying *Buddhism in Plain Terms*), all eight individuals reported significant and sustained reductions in blood glucose, alleviation of complications, and improved overall well-being. Collectively,

these testimonies suggest a consistent pattern of marked recovery associated with diligent application of these Dharma practices.

Discussion

Currently, normal glucose tolerance is defined as <5.6 mmol/L, impaired fasting glucose (pre-diabetes) as 5.6–6.9 mmol/L, and diabetes mellitus as ≥ 7.0 mmol/L [28]. Based on this standard, Case 5 (4.7) and Case 6 (5.3) achieved complete recovery. Case 3 (6.5) and Case 4 (6.5) improved to the pre-diabetes range. Case 2 (5.0–6.0) may fall into either the normal tolerance or pre-diabetes category. Cases 1 and 7 no longer require oral hypoglycemic agents, while Case 8 has completely discontinued insulin injections. These results indicate significant progress across all cases.

Such results cannot be achieved by modern medicine. Why not? The reason is simple: to cure a disease, one must first understand its underlying cause. Without identifying the root mechanism, a true cure is impossible. To date, medicine has not found the true cause of T2D, so it cannot cure T2D despite thousands of papers published. On the contrary, Master Lu revealed its underlying mechanism (Q&A 1-8), i.e., T2D is caused by karma and the spirits manifested from it. Therefore, Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door can cure it by eliminating karma and helping these spirits ascend. After karmic purification, patients restore normal blood glucose levels.

Since the Dharma discloses the true mechanism of T2D and provides a curable approach, are the scientific findings about T2D initiation and progression still relevant? Yes, although they are not considered as the root cause. Rather, they act as contributing factors that may trigger the onset of T2D or aggravate its course.

Contributing factors of T2D include genetic predisposition, obesity, family history, inactivity, environmental risks [29], gut microbiota, low-grade inflammation, lipid toxicity, and mitochondrial dysfunction [30], sleep quality [31], diet [32], among others. Following, we will use the high glycemic food as an example to illustrate how it is involved in the T2D development.

Sweet food is recognized as a major inducer of T2D, a view supported both by science [33] and by Master Lu (Q&A 1). Chronic consumption of high-sucrose diets contributes to insulin resistance, oxidative stress, and pancreatic dysfunction, ultimately impairing metabolic health and leading to T2D [34]. Once T2D has developed, even if sucrose is eliminated from the diet, the disease is not reversed. In most cases, blood glucose continues to rise over time. Medical intervention can help control glucose levels, but when standard oral medications become ineffective, insulin injections are typically required to maintain control.

Beyond a high-sugar diet, other contributors also play important roles in triggering and worsening T2D. These factors, identified by scientists through experiments and statistical analyses, are recognized as contributors or potential contributors to disease onset and progression. However, despite these findings, patients are generally unable to restore normal blood glucose after treatment. Scientists explain this by claiming that pancreatic cells cannot produce sufficient insulin or that cells have become resistant to it. But why do cells stop producing insulin? Why do they become resistant? Numerous hypotheses exist, yet none have provided a complete explanation, nor do they lead to a restoration of normal cellular function.

Viewed through the lens of Dharma, however, the picture becomes clear. T2D patients have accumulated substantial negative

karma from misconduct of body, speech, and thoughts in this life. This karma, invisible to ordinary people but seen by Master Lu, appears like black mist surrounding the body. The human physical body is immersed in this karmic mist, which behaves like hidden dynamite waiting for a trigger. Sweet foods and other risk factors act as sparks. When the time is ripe, karma is ignited, exploding like dynamite. Once karma erupts, spirits attach to the body, and illness such as diabetes develops. Thus, the occurrence of T2D signifies a strong karmic burden. Otherwise, even under the same sweet food conditions, some people do not develop T2D because their karmic weight is light or the time for retribution is not ripe.

Both karmic obstacles and spirits contribute to the damage of pancreatic beta cells, leading over time to a progressive loss of insulin-producing capacity. This process is comparable to patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD), where the glomeruli gradually lose function [35]. In both conditions, the progression is considered irreversible because, for those who do not practice Buddhism, the onset of T2D or CKD does not lessen karmic obstacles; instead, these continue to accumulate because patients continue to create new karma. Spirits are especially drawn to individuals and organs heavily burdened with karma, further exacerbating the illness and causing diabetes and CKD to worsen over time.

When cells are burdened by dense karma and afflicted by spirits, they cannot recover insulin secretion or regain insulin sensitivity. Karma acts like toxic debris, and spirits like parasites within the body; unless both are removed, true healing cannot occur. This is why Master Lu, through reading the totems of T2D patients, provides guidance on cleansing karmic obstacles and helping spirits ascend. Once this purification is accomplished, cellular function can be restored and patients can regain their health (Cases 1–8).

In short, while T2D appears to be a sugar-related problem with numerous contributing factors identified by scientific research, at its root, it is a karmic problem. This explains why, despite extensive studies at the genetic and molecular levels and the continual expansion to include every possible contributing factor, science has been unable to uncover its true mechanism, let alone provide a real cure. Our findings confirm Master Lu's teaching that T2D is fundamentally a karmic illness.

In fact, not only CKD but also other chronic diseases, such as myasthenia gravis [27], cancer [36, 37], psoriasis [38], mental disorders [39], rheumatoid arthritis [40], and epilepsy [41], share a similar pathogenic mechanism with T2D.

Karmic diseases have distinct features, including the timing of their onset. The predestined 369 calamity is one such critical period [11]. In other words, karmic eruptions often occur when the last digit of one's age is 3, 6, or 9, because karma tends to be collectively retributed at these ages. For example, in Cases 4 and 6, diabetes manifestation at the ages of 53 and 63, respectively, aligning with these karmic eruption cycles. To prevent diabetes, one must consistently eliminate karmic debts, and during the predestined 369 calamity ages in particular, make intensified efforts to clear them in order to avoid outbreaks.

Since karma is created by patients themselves, its elimination also depends on oneself. Therefore, the treatment of diabetes ultimately relies on one's own efforts and cannot be entrusted to others. However, if others are willing to help, that is an additional blessing.

In human society, when a credit card bill arrives, it is, of course, the cardholder who must pay. Asking others is useless. The bank may have money, but it will not pay your bill, because its money is not yours. Others may be wealthy, but they will not pay your debts, because the debt is yours, not theirs. This principle is easily understood by everyone.

Thus, in this sense, the Dharma is simply an extension of this worldly principle. The following story, told by Master Lu, vividly illustrates this point.

Relying on others is not as good as relying on yourself [42]

In a Buddhist parable, a man was taking shelter under the eaves from the rain when he saw Guan Yin Bodhisattva passing by with an umbrella.

He said, "Guan Yin Bodhisattva, I am so Dharma joyful to see you! Please have compassion and help me walk a section of the road."

Guan Yin Bodhisattva replied, "I am in the rain, while you are under the eaves. Since you are not getting wet, you don't need me to help you."

The man quickly stepped out into the rain, "Now, Guan Yin Bodhisattva, I am also in the rain. Shouldn't you help me now?"

Guan Yin Bodhisattva said, "You are in the rain, and I am in the rain. But I am not wet because I have an umbrella, while you are wet because you don't have one. So it is not I who am saving myself; it is the umbrella saving me. If you want salvation, don't seek it from me—go and find an umbrella yourself." With that, Guan Yin walked away.

The next day, when the man encountered difficulties, he went to a temple to pray to Guan Yin Bodhisattva. As he entered, he saw someone in front of the statue, also praying. To his surprise, that person looked exactly like Guan Yin Bodhisattva. He asked, "Excuse me, are you Guan Yin Bodhisattva?"

The person replied, "Yes, I am Guan Yin."

The man asked, "Then why are you praying to yourself?"

Guan Yin Bodhisattva said, "I also face difficulties when helping others, but I know that relying on others is not as good as relying on myself."

Many people often say to Master Lu, "Master, please save me." You must remember: relying on Master is not as good as relying on the great Buddha within your own heart. A person's success is not obtained by praying—it comes from one's own cultivation. When facing difficulties, you must use your own strength and wisdom instead of depending entirely on others. To reverse the causes of rebirth in the Six Realms, you must start cultivating today. Only by planting good causes today can you reap good results in the future.

When diabetes manifests, one should not rely solely on praying to the Bodhisattvas but must also depend on oneself, taking concrete actions to eliminate karmic debts and help spirits ascend. Only through such efforts can health be restored.

Some may imagine there are alternative ways to repay karmic debts. Yet no matter how much wealth one amasses in the human world, the underworld does not accept worldly currency. All riches become worthless after death. While certain folk practices claim to repay karmic debts, their value is minimal and their effect negligible.

Out of boundless compassion, Guan Yin Bodhisattva has already given us the true method to eliminate karma and repay karmic debts: the Five Golden Buddhist Practices of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

Conclusion

This study challenges the conventional scientific view that T2D is irreversible. While modern medicine attributes the disease to genetic, lifestyle, and molecular factors, our findings align with Master Lu's teachings that T2D is fundamentally a karmic illness.

Scientific approaches can alleviate symptoms and slow disease progression, but they cannot restore the true function of pancreatic cells or achieve lasting recovery. In contrast, the Dharma perspective recognizes karmic debts and spiritual disturbances as the root causes of diabetes. When patients actively eliminate karma and help spirits ascend through the Five Golden Buddhist Practices, cellular function may be restored and genuine recovery becomes possible. For the best outcomes, we recommend avoiding all contributing factors whenever possible, regardless of whether one has T2D or is currently healthy.

This integrative understanding not only explains why diabetes arises differently among individuals under similar conditions but also demonstrates a pathway for prevention and healing through consistent Dharma practice.

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Conflict of Interest

No.

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Ethical Statement

The author did not involve any part of the experimental design, experimental treatments and result analysis of the patients. All the experimental procedures and practices by the presenters were done by themselves independently.

Statement by Translator and Writer

The 8 Q&As and 8 case presentations in the text were translated from Chinese to English based on their intended meaning rather than a word-for-word approach. The remaining portions of the paper were written based on my limited understanding of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. If there are any inaccuracies or deviations from the true meaning of the Chinese version, or if the content does not accurately reflect Master Lu's teachings, I sincerely seek forgiveness from the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, Dharma Protectors, and Master Jun Hong Lu.

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